

INNOVATIVE CONSTRUCTION METHODS AS A FACTOR IN REDUCING PROJECT TIMELINES AND COSTS FOR COMMERCIAL AND RESIDENTIAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract

This article analyzes modern technologies and materials that contribute to accelerating construction processes and reducing costs. Innovative design and planning methods, such as Building Information Modeling (BIM) and artificial intelligence (AI), which optimize project design and management, are examined. Effective construction methods, including 3D printing and modular construction, are studied for their ability to speed up building processes. Attention is also given to the use of advanced materials, such as self-healing concrete and phase-change materials, which contribute to cost reduction.

Keywords: innovative methods, construction, Building Information Modeling (BIM), artificial intelligence (AI), 3D printing, modular construction, prefabrication, self-healing concrete, phase-change materials.

Introduction

The construction industry has long been characterized by extended project timelines and high costs. These aspects pose significant challenges for both residential and commercial developments. Traditional construction methods, while reliable, often result in inefficiencies, delays, and budget overruns due to labor-intensive processes, resource constraints, and complex logistical coordination. With increasing urbanization and demand for affordable housing and commercial spaces, there is a growing need to explore innovative approaches that can enhance efficiency, reduce construction time, and minimize costs without compromising quality.

With the increasing need for sustainable and economically viable building solutions worldwide, the construction sector is under mounting pressure to come up with new ideas. Issues like limited materials, rising labor expenses, and strict environmental rules make traditional construction methods more complicated. Industry leaders are relying on technological advancements to address these challenges, stay competitive, and fulfill market needs.

Various modern construction methods, such as modular building techniques, are becoming increasingly popular as solutions to these challenges. Through the incorporation of automation, advanced materials, and modern technology in construction, these strategies have the capacity to speed up project delivery, maximize resource utilization, and improve cost control. The purpose of this study is to examine and emphasize innovative construction techniques and materials that help decrease project timelines and expenses.

Main part. Innovative methods of design and planning in construction sector

In the construction sector, **creative design and planning methods** are becoming more important for improving project efficiency, cutting expenses, and limiting delays. Incorporating cutting-edge technologies at the beginning of construction projects boosts accuracy, fosters collaboration among stakeholders, and optimizes resource utilization.

Building Information Modeling (BIM) is one of the revolutionary technologies changing the way construction projects are designed, managed, and carried out. BIM allows for the development of virtual building

models, providing a shared digital environment for all team members involved in the project. This method makes communication and exchanging data easier, providing immediate insights into the design, materials, and structural elements. This type of process driven by a model enables better decision-making, decreasing the chances of mistakes or alterations in design while building. BIM aids the complete building lifecycle from initial design to facility maintenance using 3D, 4D, and 5D modeling techniques. The objective of utilizing BIM is to promote increased teamwork among architects, engineers, and contractors, ultimately decreasing the necessity for revisions and speeding up project schedules [3].

The utilization of **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** and **Machine Learning (ML)** is another revolutionary advancement in construction planning. AI algorithms have the ability to analyze extensive data from past projects in order to forecast potential delays, budget overruns, and lack of resources. These advancements lead to greater precision and productivity in planning, ultimately leading to more dependable and expected project results.

Utilizing advanced technologies and collaboration, this method mirrors the construction sector's dedication to efficiency and excellence throughout all project phases. In particular, AI has the potential to enhance labor efficiency by 40% and to quadruple the annual growth rates of the economy by 2035 [7]. Various ML models can optimize schedules by analyzing variables such as weather patterns, supply chain constraints, and labor availability. For example, algorithms such as decision trees are used to predict costs, spectral clustering is used to extract flat features from noisy point cloud data, especially in BIM, Bayesian networks are used to diagnose construction performance, logistic regression is commonly used to analyze factors that influence the success of the tender process [6].

Digital twin technology is gaining momentum in the construction industry as a powerful planning and design tool. A digital twin is a virtual replica of a physical asset that allows for real-time monitoring and modeling of construction projects. By creating a digital twin of a building or infrastructure before actual construction begins, project managers can simulate different

scenarios, identify potential problems, and make necessary adjustments early in the planning stage. This proactive approach reduces the likelihood of costly changes later in the project. Digital twins also enable better resource management by providing continuous tracking of materials, labor, and equipment throughout the construction process.

Innovative methods of construction and materials

The construction industry is witnessing rapid technological advancements that are transforming traditional building practices. Various innovative methods not only accelerate the construction process but also contribute to more sustainable, cost-effective, and efficient project outcomes.

One of the most adopted methods is **modular construction**. It is a method that involves manufacturing building components or modules in a controlled factory environment and then assembling them on-site. This

process offers numerous advantages over traditional construction, such as reduced construction timelines, lower costs, and minimized waste. Since the modules are fabricated off-site, work can continue in parallel with site preparation, significantly reducing overall project duration. Moreover, the factory setting ensures greater precision and quality control. Once the modules are delivered to the site, they can be quickly assembled. This approach reduces on-site labor requirements and minimizes delays caused by weather conditions.

According to 2024 report [9], the primary materials used in modular construction are predominantly wood frames, accounting for 50%, while steel frames make up 42,9%, and concrete represents 7,1%. The commercial modular construction industry spans several sectors, with multifamily housing leading the way at 20%, followed by office buildings, including government facilities (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Permanent modular construction market utilization at a glance in North America in 2024, %

Prefabrication is the manufacturing of building parts like walls, floors, and roof panels in a controlled off-site setting, much like modular construction. In contrast to fully modular buildings, prefabricated elements are usually integrated with conventional construction techniques done on-site. Pre-made concrete is frequently utilized in this procedure. The parts are made according to exact measurements and then taken to the location for putting together. Prefabrication decreases the amount of on-site labor needed and the time required for construction, enhances quality control, and reduces waste. It also improves safety by conducting most of the work in a controlled factory environment, avoiding the risks of a construction site.

3D printing technology is transforming the construction sector by allowing the fabrication of complete building structures using dedicated printers and materials. This technique, also referred to as additive manufacturing, consists of stacking building materials like

concrete, polymers, or composites to create walls, floors, and other structural components. One advantage of 3D printing is its capacity to create unique designs with intricate shapes that are challenging or costly to make using conventional building techniques. Moreover, 3D printing greatly decreases both material waste and labor expenses, since the entire construction process can be automated. This technology has been utilized in building houses, office buildings, and bridges, demonstrating its potential for widespread use in the future.

The process of 3D manufacturing is categorized into various methods, including SLA (Stereolithography), SLS (Selective Laser Sintering), FDM (Fused Deposition Modeling), DLP (Digital Light Processing), EBM (Electron Beam Melting), and LOM (Laminated Object Manufacturing), based on the types of materials utilized and the techniques for combining them (table 1).

Table 1.

Comparison of additive manufacturing methods [4]

Method	Working principle	Material used	Resolution	Strength	Roughness
FDM	Extrusion Stacking Technique	ABS, polyamide, polycarbonate, polyethylene, polypropylene and investment casting wax.	Medium	Good	Medium
SLA	Solidification of photopolymer material with UV light	Resin-based materials, acrylic, epoxy, polypropylene.	Good	Medium	Good
SLS	Sintering of powder with CO ₂ laser	Polyamide, polystyrene, carbon fiber and aluminum added polyamide, polycarbonate, stainless steel, cobalt chrome, nickel chrome, titanium, ceramic.	Weak	Good	Weak
EBM	Electron Beam Melting	Cobalt chrome and titanium alloys, ceramics.	Weak	Good	Good
LOM	Laser Cutting and Gluing of Sheets	Paper, plastic foam, metal and ceramic powder impregnated materials.	Medium	Medium	Medium

The utilization of **robotics and automation** in construction is on the rise, particularly in tasks that involve repetition, lifting heavy objects, and precise maneuvers. Robots in construction can carry out activities like laying bricks, pouring concrete, and fitting windows and doors. Drones are additionally employed for site surveys, structure inspections, and project progress monitoring, offering immediate data and decreasing the necessity for manual inspections [2]. Automated equipment enhances precision, lowers labor expenses, and increases safety on construction sites. Furthermore, robotics can also be used in dangerous settings, like high-rise building construction or underground projects, reducing dangers for human workers.

The building industry is making significant advancements in materials with innovative solutions that reduce costs, improve efficiency, and support ecological practices. **Self-repairing concrete** is seen as a groundbreaking innovation in building materials. Even though traditional concrete is durable, it can still develop cracks due to conditions like weathering, heavy loads, or structural shifts. These fissures frequently need significant upkeep and fixes, leading to an increase in the total project expenses. However, self-healing concrete includes bacteria or other substances that have the ability to fix cracks as soon as they appear. As water permeates a fissure, it stimulates bacteria to create calcium carbonate, ultimately closing the gap. This not only increases the longevity of buildings but also decreases maintenance expenses, making it a cost-efficient option for extended projects [5].

Phase-change materials (PCM) are a different creative way that helps improve the energy efficiency of buildings. PCM is capable of soaking up, retaining, and emitting heat when transitioning between solid and liquid states [1]. **Composite materials**, made by blending multiple substances to produce a new material with improved traits, are becoming more common in the field of construction. Fiberglass-reinforced polymers and carbon fiber composites are frequently utilized in bridges, facades, and other constructions that need

strong and long-lasting materials while being lightweight [8].

Utilizing innovative techniques such as modular construction, 3D printing, and advanced materials like self-healing concrete and phase-change materials marks a major advancement for the construction sector. These methods not just decrease construction time and expenses but also enhance the longevity and eco-friendliness of structures.

Conclusion

Advancements in design and construction techniques are leading to a major transformation in the construction industry. Cutting-edge techniques like BIM, AI-driven strategies, and digital twins are transforming the initial phases of project creation. These instruments boost teamwork, streamline resource distribution, and enable more precise project prediction, diminishing the chances of expensive setbacks or mistakes. At the same time, new construction techniques and materials are changing the way buildings are built. The use of modular construction, 3D printing, and advanced materials such as self-healing concrete and phase-changing materials is greatly decreasing project schedules and enhancing sustainability.

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